

THE ROLE OF THE ENERGY SECTOR IN NATIONAL ECONOMIES.

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Annotation: *The article describes the acceleration of economic development of the world and individual countries in terms of the composition and volume of extraction, production and consumption of energy resources and their demand for energy resources.*

Keywords: *Energy, oil, natural gas, coal, uranium, hydrogen energy, nuclear energy, electricity, solar energy.*

Energy plays an important role in human and social life, increasing their ability to meet different needs. The development of human civilization has always been closely linked to the amount and type of energy used.

The reason for the global tragedy facing the present generation is that during the twentieth century, especially in the last 40 years, people's use of energy for economic development has increased significantly. This has a negative impact on the environment. This is because global warming is directly related to emissions from thermal power plants that use fossil fuels, as well as emissions from an increasing number of internal combustion engines.

In the last 50 years, more fossil fuels have been mined than ever before. The current century is no exception. Today, the world's fuel consumption is 12 billion tons of oil equivalent per year (about 2 tons of oil per capita). The demand for fossil fuels is growing rapidly.

Fossil fuels such as oil, natural gas, coal and uranium currently form the basis of the global energy balance and will continue to do so in the near future. However, these fuel resources, their processing and use are declining.

According to the current level of use of energy resources, the world's oil reserves are 45-50 years, natural gas 70-75 years, coal 165-170 years, lignite 450-500 years, and nuclear fuel was expected to last for relatively more years.

The hydropower potential of rivers, reservoirs and irrigation canals, solar, wind energy, biomass (including energy from domestic waste), rising water and ocean wave energy, and geothermal energy are reflected in alternative forms of energy.

Theoretically, renewable energy sources offer great potential for their widespread use. However, the associated financial costs and the conditions that must be met for the production of such energy reduce the attractiveness of these sources to some extent.

Hydrogen power, on the other hand, is currently considered to be less environmentally friendly. However, further development and improvement of hydrogen extraction processes can change this situation for the better.

Today, as nuclear energy is considered as a solution to the problem of energy supply aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, the radioactive waste of this technology should not be forgotten. Their harmful effects can last for thousands of years, so radioactive waste must be disposed of in safe places (sarcophagi).

Undoubtedly, efficient production and rational use of energy is the most convenient way to conserve our natural resources and prevent environmental degradation. Development and introduction of new energy technologies (joint production of heat and electricity, fuel cells, coal gasification, liquid synthetic fuels), increase fuel and energy efficiency, large-scale renewable energy production great work is being done to increase the share of renewable energy sources.

Diagram 1. The structure of energy supply in the world

Source: UN report on clean energy for the rural population of Karakalpakstan (Phase II). UNDP 2021.

Consumption of energy by consumers is also an important issue. We need to use energy more wisely. The goal is to reduce the supply of valuable resources, not to

adversely affect the pollution and degradation of the environment, and not to waste energy. This approach requires setting a price for energy that is close to the cost of producing it, as well as focusing on the production of efficient energy equipment and the formation of the concept of energy saving in the minds of the population.

Most of the government support measures used in many countries around the world are expected to be gradually introduced in Uzbekistan. Before Uzbekistan decides to put renewable energy sources into practice and to introduce certain forms of state support, it must first formulate its overall Energy Strategy, which includes the development of renewable energy. must determine its location. Only then will it be necessary to decide how and to what extent to support the development of such technologies, to support local production, which will replace new imported technologies.

Uzbekistan is a country with a large renewable energy potential, which is three times the production of all types of fossil fuels. Solar-based technologies have great potential in Uzbekistan. Because this type of renewable energy can be used throughout the country throughout the year. Increasing the use of solar energy could easily meet the country's need for electricity and heat, especially in remote and inaccessible rural areas, and allow large volumes of natural gas to be diverted for export.

Uzbekistan faces certain challenges in electricity supply. This is particularly noticeable in rural areas where 60 percent of the population lives. Modernization and reconstruction of power plants, energy supply and distribution networks are among the priorities of industrial development in the country. The development of renewable energy will help to eliminate the need to build long-distance transmission lines to connect remote settlements to the power grid, while providing reliable energy and significantly reducing energy supply losses. Currently, the country's energy balance has a small share of renewable energy produced only by small hydropower plants. Although the potential of other renewable energy sources is great, the share of their use is still small.

As we focus on economic development, we must also think about conserving our natural resources and preventing environmental degradation. Much work is being done to develop new energy technologies and to use fuel and energy more efficiently. However, increasing the amount of energy produced using renewable energy sources can only increase energy efficiency.

At present, the population does not have enough information about renewable energy sources and lacks scientific and practical experience in the use of solar and wind energy. This is the case in many developing countries. They need to move forward with the technological development of renewable energy, create an economic environment that allows the private sector to use solar and wind energy, and thus increase the share of renewable energy in the country's energy balance.

One such important measure is to set prices that reflect the real value of conventional energy fuels and energy, thereby using efficient energy equipment and inculcating energy-saving ideas in the minds of the population.

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